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ISSN: 2588-1582

Frequency: 2 issues / year

eISSN: 2588-1582

Editorial Members' Guide

Practical Guidelines for NAJFNR Editors 2020

Version updated and approved by the Advisory Board Editors

The North African Journal of Food and Nutrition Research

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4023997>

Preamble

The North African Journal of Food and Nutrition Research (NAJFNR) is an international, peer-reviewed, open access, online journal, with no charges for submission, processing or publication of manuscripts

The NAJFNR is endorsed by the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research and The General Research Directorate (DGRSDT).

The journal is committed to the rapid publication of the latest laboratory and clinical findings in all fields of human nutrition and food sciences.

Manuscripts of original research, review, short communication/report, case report, hypothesis formation, expert opinion, and commentary are all considered for publication.

The primary purpose of the NAJFNR is to act as a source of information usable by researchers and practitioners to enrich their knowledge about nutrition and its development in developing countries and primarily in North African ones.

The aim of the following guide is to provide the editorial members all useful information concerning their tasks and assignments towards the journal.

Pr. Meghit Boumediene KHALED
Editor-in-Chief/Founder

Aims and Scope of the journal

The North African Journal of Food and Nutrition Research is a peer-reviewed, open access journal that publishes original research articles, review articles, short communications, clinical studies, in all areas of nutrition, food sciences, and metabolism.

The journal hosts the proceedings of relevant congresses and presents shorter notices focused on the original character of the Mediterranean and North African nutritional civilization. In addition, this journal is intended as to be a platform for scientific debate and knowledge-sharing among students, professionals and researchers, and between them and the broader scientific community, and finally as a tool making nutrition a development priority in Africa through improving nutrition knowledge, raising awareness of nutritional disorders, and reducing the high socioeconomic burden associated with diet-related diseases).

The average time between submission and the final decision is 45 days. The time between acceptance and online publication is less than 15 days.

Papers with a major focus on traditional medicine will not be accepted.

Direct rejection: Submitted manuscript can be rejected after initial review by an editor if there is a lack of rigor or novelty or considered inappropriate or of insufficient importance for publication in the NAJFNR. Therefore, it will not be reviewed if they fail to match the aims and scope of the journal, or if it does not conform to standard English usage and does not meet the formatting requirements.

Specific topics covered in the journal include :

- Food Composition and Dietary Intake Assessment
- Epidemiology, Nutrition-Related Disorders such as Obesity, Diabetes, Dyslipidemias, etc.
- Biochemistry and Cellular Metabolism of Nutrients
- Dietary Strategies and Nutrition Education
- Food and Nutritional Security and Challenges
- Diet, eating behaviors and health
- Public Health Policy & Health Economics
- Nutrition and Cancer
- Food Chemistry and Engineering
- Human Clinical Nutrition
- Food Processing, Packaging and Labeling
- Nutrition, Physical Activity and Sport
- Infant, Child, and Adolescent Nutrition
- Nutrition and Immune-regulation
- Nutrition and Reproduction
- Food Environment and non-communicable diseases (NCDs)

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF AND MANAGER EDITOR

Editor-in-Chief and Manager Editor Responsibilities and duties

Editor-in-Chief and Manager editor responsibilities are:

- Ensuring the academic quality of the journal to represent the full breadth of nutrition, reflecting the interests and objectives of the NAJFNR;
- Taking responsibility for appointment of the Editorial Board;
- Providing Authors with Quality Guidelines/Instructions on the process of preparation and submission of manuscripts, which describe everything that is expected of them;
- Providing Authors with the Journal's Policy and Ethics;
- Providing a description of peer review processes;
- Informing Authors that the submission is evaluated according to the standard procedures of the journal;
- Establishing a system for an effective and timely peer review;
- Making editorial decisions timely;
- Informing Authors of manuscripts that it is inappropriate to manipulate citations;
- Establishing a procedure for reconsidering of the editorial decisions;
- Making sure that the Editor shall refrain from using confidential information for personal gain, and shall take reasonable steps to ensure that such information is not used for the advantage of other parties;
- Acting professionally, without prejudice or conflict of interest. The Editor will not allow their editorial judgment to be influenced by political, commercial and other considerations that are beyond the scope of each scientific report and analysis of possible impacts and applications;
- And Communicating all other editorial policies and standards clearly.

→ Responsibilities toward Readers

Editor-in-Chief has the responsibility to make clear and rational editorial decisions to ensure the best selection of content that contributes to the development of scientific knowledge, and inform the readers.

Editor's responsibilities to Readers are:

- Providing literature references and authors' contact information so interested readers may pursue further discourse.
- Creating mechanisms to determine if the journal provides what readers need and want.
- Disclosing all relevant potential conflicts of interest of those involved in considering a manuscript or affirming that none exists.
- Providing a mechanism for a further discussion on the scientific significance of a paper, such as by publishing letters to the Editor, article blogs or other forms of public discourse.
- Stating the journal policies regarding ethics, embargo, submission and publication fees, and accessibility of content.

SPECIALTY AND ASSOCIATE EDITORS

HOW TO BECOME ASSOCIATE OR SPECIALTY EDITOR?

If you are interested and motivated to join our editorial board as an associate or specialty editor, one of the ways is through a direct application letter to the Editor-in-chief. This may happen as a result of your expertise in a specific field of nutrition.

WHAT WOULD THE CRITERIA FOR AN EDITOR POSITION?

- Expertise and experience in the specialist field related to the NAJFNR (<https://www.najfnr.org/aims-and-scope>);
- Publication record of a number of articles and/or books (usually in/related to the specialist field);
- Being a reviewer for an international peer reviewed journal;
- Having a PhD qualification or a senior research position with equivalent experience in research and scholarship;
- Enthusiasm to undertake the Editor role, by ensuring recognition of all aspects of the reality of the role and the work involved.

THE MAIN ROLE AND DUTIES OF A JOURNAL EDITOR

One of the key roles of a Journal Editor is to promote scholarship in the specialist field associated with the journal.

➔ **Editor's responsibilities toward Reviewers**

Possessing a good Panel of Reviewers constitutes an issue for any journal. One of the ways is to invite Reviewers with expertise in the subject areas related to the journal. The other way is to invite Authors who have published in the journal. Invited Reviewers should be aware of the total time spent on the review and giving prompt feedback to the Editors. They should also communicate with Editors regularly so that they can quickly provide feedback. Authors can suggest at least three (3) reviewers but not from the same institution.

- Providing Quality Guidelines for peer reviewing of manuscripts.
- Establishing a process for Reviewers to ensure that they consider the manuscript as a confidential document and complete the peer review promptly.
- Assigning papers for review according to each Reviewer's area of interest and expertise.
- Providing the Journal's Policy and Ethics for Reviewers.
- Requesting that Reviewers identify any potential conflicts of interest and asking that they disclose it to the Editor when responding.
- Allowing Reviewers appropriate time to make their reviewer's reports.
- Requesting reviews at a valid frequency.
- Finding ways to recognize the contributions of Reviewers.

Specialty Editor

Specialty Editor will need to encourage new and established Authors to submit articles and set up a reliable Panel of Expert Reviewers.

- ➔ The Specialty Editor has responsibilities toward:
- the Associate Editors of the same specialty
 - the Peer Reviewers
 - the journal's readers

The Specialty Editor should normally check the manuscripts to see if they meet the minimum criteria for publication in the journal. The Editor may sometimes reject manuscripts without peer review. Reasons for this practice are usually that the paper:

- is beyond the scope of the NAJFNR;
- does not meet the quality standards of the journal;
- is not sufficiently novel;
- is of limited scientific merit.

Associate Editor

As the Specialty Editor does, Associate Editor needs to encourage new and established Authors to submit manuscripts for publication and set up a reliable Panel of Expert Reviewers (at least 2 reviewers per manuscript).

➔ Besides, the Associate Editor has to contact on a regular basis:

- the Authors
- the Reviewers.

Editors' decisions to accept or to reject a manuscript for publication should be based on the importance, originality and clarity of the manuscript and its relevance to the aims and scope of the journal.

In general, the Editor is looking for essential characteristics in an article in order to maintain the quality of the journal.

➔ Citation Manipulation

Citation manipulation refers to any practice that pressures Authors to cite material with the primary goal of boosting citation rates. The world's scientific community considers all such practices unacceptable.

IMPORTANT

- We ask that both, Specialty (SE) and Associate Editors (AE), should submit an inaugural article **within 6 months** of their appointment to NAJFNR. An inaugural article can be of any article type, such as original research, review or perspective, in area of expertise related to the specialty. This content is integral to raising interest in the journal by bringing an audience of readers and potential authors to your specialty.
- The term of appointment of Associate Editors is limited to a period of three (03) years, renewable to six (06) years, depending on activity. Changes also occur in the meantime, if a member resigns, leaves the editorial for other reasons or the journal revoked by the Editor-in-Chief who remains the chairperson of the board, hence allowed to take the final decision in any regard.
- SE and AE should influence the quality of the journal, they must ensure to attract new authors in their communities where they work and encourage new submissions. However, editors can propose well-justified themes in order to publish them in a particular or additional issue.
- The decision of selecting new scopes are taken by absolute majority. In the case of a tie, the voice of the Editor-in-Chief shall prevail.
- If a member of the editorial board submits an article to a predatory journal or publisher, or is a co-editor/reviewer he/she will be automatically revoked from the editorial board. You can find the list of predatory journals and publishers in these links:
<https://predatoryjournals.com>
<https://beallslist.net>
<https://www.openaccessjournal.com/assets/PDF/List-of-Predatory-Journals-2019.pdf>
<https://jefferson.libguides.com/c.php?g=250298&p=1666257>

ADVISORY EDITORS

Advisory Editor

The NAJFNR believes that Advisory editors (Ad-E) are the heart of the journal who should add value and academic credibility. They constitute an integral part of the editorial workflow and should be actively engaged to directing the journal's future and consider its innovative developments. Their role is therefore crucial to the continued success.

Ad-E provides input, suggestions and specialized scientific support in journal management. Ad-E is expected to work directly with the Editor-in-chief and to advise him on topics that should be addressed by the journal as well as the overall scope and focus of the journal. Furthermore, Ad-E will be consulted to explore their views and perspectives on the roles and tasks of peer reviewers.

The responsiveness of our Advisory editors to date has been outstanding. Despite the many competing demands on their time, every member makes a regular effort to share the benefit of their knowledge and experience with our editorial staff.

In conjunction with the other components of the Editorial Board, the Ad-E members will act as ambassadors for NAJFNR throughout the scientific community.

REVIEW EDITORS

Review Editors

→ Peer Reviewer responsibilities toward authors

- Providing written, unbiased feedback in a timely manner on the scholarly merits and the scientific value of the work, together with the documented basis for the reviewer's opinion
- Indicating whether the writing is clear, concise, and relevant and rating the work's composition, scientific accuracy, originality, and interest to the journal's readers
- Avoiding personal comments or criticism
- Maintaining the confidentiality of the review process: not sharing, discussing with third parties, or disclosing information from the reviewed paper

→ Peer Reviewer responsibilities toward editors

- Notifying the editor immediately if unable to review a manuscript in a timely manner and providing the names of potential other reviewers
- Alerting the editor about any potential personal or financial conflict of interest and declining to review when a possibility of a conflict exists
- Complying with the editor's written instructions on the journal's expectations for the scope, content, and quality of the review
- Providing a thoughtful, fair, constructive, and informative critique of the submitted work, which may include supplementary material provided to the journal by the author
- Determining scientific merit, originality, and scope of the work; indicating ways to improve it; and recommending acceptance or rejection using whatever rating scale the editor deems most useful
- Noting any ethical concerns, such as any violation of accepted norms of ethical treatment of animal or human subjects or substantial similarity between the reviewed manuscript and any published paper or any manuscript concurrently submitted to another journal which may be known to the reviewer
- Refraining from direct author contact

EDITORIAL OFFICE ASSISTANTS

Editorial Assistants

WHAT IS THE MAIN ROLE OF THE EDITORIAL ASSISTANT?

The Editorial Office Assistants work directly with the Specialty and Associate Editors to coordinate the reviewing and publishing process. The Editorial Team agrees with the Editor the content of each issue and sends to the authors the Editor information concerning all manuscripts in their various stages of the editorial process.

Editorial Office Assistants may also handle a variety of office or administrative tasks, such as filing information on the status of manuscripts; scheduling, attending and summarizing meetings; and handling routine phone calls, emails and correspondence.

NB. For all Editors**Citation Manipulation**

Some Authors cite material with the primary goal of boosting their citation rates. The NAJFNR considers all such practices unacceptable.

The following forms of citation manipulation should be reported:

- Editors request that Authors add citations from their own journal or a disproportionate number of articles from their own journal are cited.
- Authors cite a large number of their own published articles.
- Reviewers suggest citing their own papers.
- A group of colleagues frequently cites each other's articles.

Considering appeals for rejected manuscripts

Editor makes the best efforts to solicit unbiased peer reviews to evaluate manuscripts fairly and to make decisions that are in the best interest of the journal and its readers. Despite of these Editors' best efforts Authors may still want to contest editorial decisions.

Editor should state a policy in place to address appeals and help resolve these issues:

- Determine whether the decision was clearly explained to the Author and whether it may have been based on wrong or questionable information;
- Reconsider rejected papers if the Author provides justified reasons why the decision may have been wrong;
- Encourage re-submission of papers that are possibly acceptable but were rejected because major revision was required. Provide precise explanation on what is necessary to make the paper acceptable.